

FINANCING POLICIES FOR INCLUSIVE EDUCATION SYSTEMS (FPIES)

All European countries are moving towards greater educational inclusion. Promoting equity in educational opportunities is a clear strategic challenge for the European countries. Countries' systems of funding for education play a critical role in implementing the right to education and in developing inclusive education systems that promote participation and achievement for all learners. Effective inclusive education requires coherent financing mechanisms that promote flexibility in educational opportunities and support arrangements across sectors to provide meaningful educational experiences.

Through work with policy-makers for inclusive education and a series of detailed case studies examining very different educational funding approaches, the Financing Policies for Inclusive Education Systems (FPIES) project will identify what coherent financing mechanisms for inclusive education look like, how they operate and what critical levers impact upon the effectiveness of funding policy mechanisms to reduce disparities in learning outcomes affecting all learners.

Partnership project

The FPIES project is funded by the European Commission as a **Forward Looking Cooperation Project**. The project is based on direct co-operation between eight partners: the Ministries of Education in Italy, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal and Slovenia, the Universitat Ramon Llull, Spain, and the European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education.

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More information about the project partners can be found on their respective websites:

- **Ministry of Education, University and Research, Italy**
- **Ministry of Education and Science, Lithuania**
- **Ministry of Education, Culture and Science, Netherlands**
- **Ministry of Education and Research, Norway**
- **Ministry of Education, Portugal**
- **Ministry of Education, Science and Sport, Slovenia**
- **Universitat Ramon Llull**
- **European Agency for Special Needs and Inclusive Education**

As Evaluation Partner, Universitat Ramon Llull will conduct an on-going process evaluation to inform decision-making and implementation of specific project tasks. Furthermore, ministerial representatives from the Agency's 29 member countries will identify their specific priorities for detailed examination and provide feedback on final project outputs.

Within the FPIES project, trans-national co-operation is a critical factor in ensuring policy relevant outcomes that have the potential for up-scaling and positive impacts on inclusive education at national and European levels.

Aims and objectives

The FPIES project activities will aim to:

- build on existing work to develop, trial and evaluate a coherent methodology for examining financing policy issues, developments and challenges in European countries;
- conduct a detailed analysis of financing policy issues for inclusive education, leading to the development of concrete policy tools that can be used for developing more inclusive funding approaches and financing policies that reduce disparities in education and work towards all learners' educational and social inclusion and well-being.

The main project output will be a validated open-source Policy Guidance Tool on financing policies that aim to reduce disparities in education and work towards all learners' educational and social inclusion and well-being.

Further information

For more information about the FPIES project, please visit the **project website** or the **dedicated project area** on the European Commission website.

Contact the FPIES project team via **secretariat@european-agency.org**